
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN SOUTH EAST

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Abstract: *Given the speed of technological change and its relevant for businesses especially small and medium enterprises (SMEs) to move along with this change prompted the study to determine information technology and performance of small and medium enterprises in south east as a broad objective. The study was anchored on the unified theory of Acceptance and use of Technology model. The population of this study was drawn from SMEs in the five states in the Southeast Nigeria that involved 366 SMEs, descriptive survey research design was employed in this study and the study relied on secondary and primary data, it considered not sampling data as all the selected SMEs were used and complete enumeration was adopted.. Simple regression analysis was used to analysis the hypotheses. The study revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between software development, digital literacy and data management on performance of SMEs in Southeast Nigeria. The study indicate that information technology contribute to SMEs performance positively. The study recommended among others that SMEs owners and managers should be committed in getting used to information technology through digital literacy that will help develop business software and also secure their business data through database management for an improved performance of Small and Medium Enterprise SMEs in the Southeast Nigeria.*

Keywords: *Information Technology, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), Digital Literacy, Software Development, Business Performance*

Introduction

Today's most technologically advanced economies are truly knowledge based (Syed, 2018, He, Zhang, & Li 2021). There is a gradual movement from industrial economy to a knowledge economy, as number of scholars and commentators have argued that the leading edge of the economy in developed countries has become driven by technologies based on knowledge and information production and dissemination, most countries in the world are moving from an economic growth that is dependent on

a country's ability to create, accumulate and disseminate knowledge (Tob-Ogu, Kumar, & Cullen 2018). Thus, to compete in the knowledge economy, countries need a strong IT literate skills base that can innovate and adapt quickly to change (He, et al, 2021). Information systems and technology can play a significant role in improving small and medium enterprises (Bardhan, Chen, & Karahanna 2020, He, et al, 2021). Technological advance, like many aspects of economic and social life, is often characterized by a feedback process in which early success is heavily rewarded. Computers and the internet catalyzed the growth of the knowledge economy by enabling people to put knowledge into a digital form easily transmitted to anywhere around the world (Johannesson, & Jorgensen, 2017). The pace of globalization and increase the complexity of business practices resulting from IT speeding up because firms not only need to be familiar with their local context but also with global developments (Hameed, Naveed, 2019). Many countries such as India, the Republic of Korea, Taiwan and China have created enabling environments to ensure that SMEs are well positioned to capture these emerging business opportunities (Ayandibu, & Houghton, 2017). SMEs outside the IT sector have also benefited by adopting ICT in their own operations, enabling them to communicate quickly, increase productivity, develop new business opportunities, and connect to global networks (Ayandibu, & Houghton, 2017). The Information Technology concept is a new development that has changed ways and manner of doing things, in commerce, trade, agriculture, and manufacturing and government services, it is to be adopted by business as a matter of responding to world dynamics (Hameed & Naveed 2019). Highlighting the impact of IT in recent years, Diehr, and Wilhelm, (2017) and He, et al, (2021) observed that the 1990s witness the proliferation and hyper growth of internet and internet technologies, which together are creating a global and cost-effective platform for business to communicate and conduct commerce (Syed, 2018, Kurbonov & Istamova 2021).

Today SMEs worldwide play a significant role in the economy (Islam, Khan, Obaidullah & Alam, 2011). At present the vibrant SME sector is identified as engine of growth playing a significant role in economic growth, innovation, employment generation and poverty reduction (Mavondo, 2011). SMEs have become important as a source of employment that maximizes the efficiency of resource allocation and distribution, as well as mobilizing and utilizing local human and material resources (Cunningham & Rowley, 2007). SMEs also act as suppliers of goods and service to large organizations. Most SMEs are characterized as dynamic, innovative, and efficient and their small size allows for flexibility, immediate feedback, short decision making chain, better understanding and quicker response to customer needs (Singh, Garg & Deshmukh, 2008). There are very few studies about IT adoption in developing countries, (Olaleye, Sanusi, & Salo, 2019). Investigating adoption of information technology in South East Nigerian, it was found that SMEs have major factors inhibiting IT diffusion and intensive utilization is poor physical infrastructure. Despite the importance of IT and emphasis by various governments to encourage SMEs to adopt IT, it has been reported that SMEs have been slow in adopting IT for various reasons. (Olaleye et al, 2019, Pramono et al., 2021).

The dynamic role of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in developing countries can never be overemphasized as they contribute significantly towards socio-economic objectives by providing innovative and creative jobs, entrepreneurship and industrial development (Chege, Wang, and Suntu, 2019, Adanlawo, Vezi-Magigaba & Owolabi, 2021), Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) face several challenges in adopting and utilizing information technology (IT). These include limited financial resources, lack of necessary IT skills and training, difficulty in finding and retaining IT professionals, and misalignment of IT with business strategies. Additionally, SMEs may struggle with the cost of implementing and maintaining IT infrastructure, lack of awareness about the benefits of IT, and insufficient government support.

Similarly, Small businesses have a lot of competition when it comes to hiring employees with an adequate skill set required for solving IT issues. Larger companies have the advantage in that they can offer higher salaries and better benefits, so SMEs may have to outsource their IT staff to reduce costs. Starting from the local government system to the state level especially in Nigeria, there has been a problem of poor electricity supply, inflation, cost of raw materials, insurance costs, low demand for products and services, lack of innovation which affects employee competence of the SMEs, lack of skill acquisition which affects business idea retentions of the SMEs, skill retention which affects market sustainability of the SMEs and other general business costs. However, SMEs in South east region of Nigeria are incapacitated by several factors militating against their IT growth, absence of informal access to loan; stumpy level of technological cognizance and enhancement; poor infrastructural facilities; shortage of skills ad competences; low level of entrepreneurial skills and entrepreneurial mindset; lack of formidable and qualified employees that results in poor performance, efficiency and growth.

This study determines the effect of information technology on performance of small and medium enterprises in south east. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the effect of software development on the performance of small and medium enterprises in Southeast, Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the effect of digital literacy on the performance of small and medium enterprises in Southeast, Nigeria.
3. Determine the effect of database management on the performance of small and medium enterprises in Southeast, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Concept of Information Technology

The term Information Technology (IT) relates to the utilization of technology for the purpose of processing, storing, retrieving, and disseminating information (Kamar et al., 2022). Information technology (IT) is a set of related fields within information and communications technology (ICT), that encompass computer systems, software, programming languages, data and

information processing, and storage. Information technology is an application of computer science and computer engineering. Its a process involve the use of computer systems, both hardware and software, in addition with computer networks and telecommunications facilities to gather, retain, manipulate, scrutinize, and convey data. An information technology system (IT system) is generally an information system, a communications system, or, more specifically speaking, a computer system including all hardware, software, and peripheral equipment ,Computing, data communications, information systems, database management, information security, software development encompasses a multitude of components in Information Technology and other related areas. The important of technology is pervasive, including a wide range of domains such as commerce, academia, governance, leisure, medical care, communication, and various other spheres. Information Technology is a widely tool used in the corporate sector, serving to streamline data processing, automate business operations, optimize operational efficiency, bolster performance, fortify information security, and enable informed decision-making (Kraugusteeliana et al., 2022). Organizations and SMEs employ information technology (IT) to handle customer data, streamline supply chain operations, establish and sustain database systems, disseminate information via computer networks, among other functions (Harahap, Sutrisno, et al., 2023). Information Technology has a significant impact on various aspects of our daily lives, including communication, work, education and businesses. As a key components of a knowledge economy include a greater reliance on intellectual capabilities than on physical inputs or natural resources, combined with efforts to integrate improvements in every stage of the production process It It utilizes electronic devices such as computers and mobile phones to gain access to the internet, engaging in social media to communicate with others, exchanging electronic mail, performing online searches, engaging in e-commerce transactions, and other comparable undertakings (Hopia et al., 2023)

Small and Medium Enterprises, SMEs

In Schumpeter's theory, knowledge was not the outcome of an economic process but good to be exploited by small and medium enterprises in their innovative economic processes. In this context, Schumpeter (2003) opines that SME's process is a major factor in economic development and the entrepreneur is the key to economic growth whatever the form of economic and political set-up of a country, SME's is indispensable for economic development. Sunusi (2009) states that SMEs are critical components of economic development as they account for more than 50 percent of GDP of developing economies. Some aspects of economic life were taken for granted in the industrial age, surprisingly enough, one of the scarcest resources of all knowledge was treated as given and inflexible in its supply, just like minerals and other natural resources. According to National Bureau of statistics (2018) the national unemployment rate for Nigeria between 2013 and 2018 showed that unemployment persons constituted 18.1% in 2013, 19.4% in 2014, 19.6% in 2015, 21.0% in 2016, 23.7% in 2017 and 34.0% in 2018 with respect to age group, education and sex. NBS (2018) data

showed the persons aged between 15 and 24 years has 30.3% and between 25 and 44 years, 44% were unemployed. The unemployment rate in Nigeria as at (2017) was high. Nigeria had a population of 164.38 million in 2011. Out of this figure the labour forces stood at 67.25 million out of which 57.05 million were employed and 16.07 million unemployed (NBS, 2018). More generally, the development of SMEs is seen as accelerating the achievement of wider economic and socio-economic objectives, including poverty alleviation (Napitupulu et al., 2018). Notwithstanding the recognition of the important roles SMEs play in these countries, their development is largely constrained by a number of factors, such as lack of access to appropriate technology; limited access to international markets, the existence of laws, regulations and rules that impede the development of the sector; weak institutional capacity, lack of management skills and training, and most importantly finance (Adanlawo et al, 2021). While some of these factors such as financing have received adequate attention in the literature, some of them, such as technology, have not (Chege & Wang, 2019). Investment in technology and keeping up with information technology (IT) is increasingly important to all firms (Farag et al, 2019). Technology plays a crucial role in the development of new SMEs. Technology not only helps in SMEs, growth and development. During the 19th and 20th centuries, two opposing assumptions have emerged out of this basic idea. The first assumption is associated with David Ricardo, in his world, different regions were assumed to be endowed with differing sets of technological and commercial knowledge. Chege and Wang, (2019) noted that information technological has the highest likelihood of making a difference if it is integrated into structured business processes and used by people with the knowledge and training needed to interpret it and apply it correctly. Niebel, (2018) and Adanlawo et al, (2021) assert that the influence of technology goes beyond isolated behavioral changes for the optimization of organizational productivity; it also, affects the culture prevalent in the organization. The synergetic combination of SME's and such potential information technological knowledge was enough to make the general equilibrium unstable. There is by definition also, a decline of profitability that would sooner or later force the SME's into a frantic search for new ideas and innovations. As such, the sustainability of SMEs should be the number one priority of every developing country of which Nigeria is not an exception. The last three decades of development within "cognitive science" have credited the process of interaction with the fundamentally important role of knowledge accumulation in industrial and other organizations. It has also become more important to clarify the precise meaning of knowledge in contrast to information. Some of the conceptual issues delimiting the capabilities of computers from those of human intelligence are discussed in the contribution to this volume regarding to information technology that is replacing industrial economy to knowledge economy.

Information Technology a component of knowledge economy in enhancing performance of SME's

Ideas of computer science were first mentioned before the 1950s under the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) and Harvard University, where they had discussed and began thinking of computer circuits and numerical calculations. As time went on, the field of information technology and computer science became more complex and was able to handle the processing of more data. Scholarly articles began to be published from different organizations (Slotten, 2014). During the early computing; Alan Turing, J. Presper Eckert, and John Mauchly were considered some of the major pioneers of computer technology in the mid-1900s. Giving them such credit for their developments, most of their efforts were focused on designing the first digital computer. Along with that, topics such as artificial intelligence began to be brought up as Turing was beginning to question such technology of the time period, (Henderson, 2017). Viscio and Pasternack (1998) is of the view that technology gave birth to the information economy and transformed into the knowledge economy. Information and fast access to information have thus become an integral part of the knowledge economy. According to Ram, Noel and Tichy (1998), the ideas, technology and capital to satisfy new needs flow freely, thus creating huge growth opportunities of SME's, SME's, performance is therefore determined by a combination of technical and social factors, i.e. people, culture, structure and systems. By combining all these factors, SME's has a better chance of continuous and sustained improvement and innovation. The main driving force behind the knowledge economy is the use of ideas, i.e. knowledge, rather than physical ability. This is also highlighted by Brinkley (Work Foundation, n.d:19-23), who states that the knowledge economy is the result of what you get when organizations bring together technology and "well-educated minds" in order to be profitable. The knowledge economy can also be viewed as an extension of the post-industrial, information society. This new economic reality has emerged in recent years as a result of advances in technology that have changed the nature of knowledge creation and use. Technology needs to be applied to organize information into meaningful chunks of knowledge and the emphasis has moved away from transforming raw materials or the exploitation of cheap labour. As a result, business leaders are focusing more attention on intangible goods and services such as software programs and databases which require human intelligence to create or deliver and less on tangible assets such as machinery or equipment. The term "knowledge economy" was coined in the late 1990s after the widespread adoption of personal computers and the Internet made it possible for people to share information more easily than ever before and why got to information technology that is as well healthy for Small and medium enterprises as their services as a sector have become increasingly important players, in terms of both economic growth and employment. More and more countries, especially developing countries, have a strong governmental focus on developing these enterprises, due to their importance in the economy. AFredman and Dell (1999) emphasize that the internet (i.e. technology) has changed the way in which we do business.

Technology has enabled the world to get a lot smaller, i.e. globalization. The UN Millennium Project (2005; Juma & Agwara, 2006) states that small and medium enterprises account for more than 90% of the private sector worldwide. It is important for these enterprises to continually develop and improve. They will thus ensure that they transform their knowledge into goods and services. This transformation will, in turn, have a positive impact on the economy. Africa is thus faced with promoting the establishment of small and medium enterprises if it wishes to become knowledge productive in the knowledge economy

Software development on the performance of small and medium enterprises

Software development is the process of designing and implementing a software solution to satisfy a user. The process is more encompassing than programming, writing code, in that it includes conceiving the goal, evaluating feasibility, analyzing requirements, design, testing and release. The process is part of software engineering which also includes organizational management, project management, configuration management and other aspects. Software development involves many skills and job specializations including programming, testing, documentation, graphic design, user support, marketing, and fundraising. Software development involves many tools including: compiler, integrated development environment (IDE), version control, computer-aided software engineering, and word processor. In today's digital landscape, small businesses are increasingly turning to software solutions to streamline operations, enhance efficiency, and expand their market reach, as the demand for tailored software solutions rises, small business software development companies have become essential partners for these enterprises (Chilingaryan, 2024). For Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), this frequently entails shifting from manual, paper-based procedures to automated digital systems and workflows driven by software, cloud computing, mobile technologies, and data analytics (Tronvoll et al., 2021). Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are increasingly leveraging a variety of emerging technological tools to enhance their operations, improve efficiency, and stay competitive in the market (Oyewole et al., 2024). Some of these tools include Cloud Computing, Big Data Analysis, Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, Block chain, Robotic Process Automation, Cybersecurity Solutions. For firms aiming to stay ahead or expand into new markets, embracing new technologies is imperative (Vasile & Iriart, 2023). Innovation in technology significantly impacts an enterprise competitive edge. Software solutions for SME's are designed with the specific goals of streamlining workflows, automating repetitive tasks, and optimizing business processes. By automating manual processes and integrating disparate systems and data sources, these soft-wares enables small businesses to operate more efficiently, minimize errors, and improve overall productivity (Solvefy, 2024). This efficiency gain translates into cost savings, time savings, and greater capacity to focus on core business activities and strategic initiatives. Software development for SME's offers small businesses a powerful tool for addressing their unique challenges, achieving operational excellence,

driving growth, enhance performance and success in today's digital economy. (Solvefy, 2024) opined that SME's venturing into software solutions tailored to their specific needs can enhance efficiency, productivity, gain a competitive advantage, and ensure scalability, flexibility, security and improve performance. As technology continues to play a central role in business operations and strategy, software development remains a crucial investment for small businesses looking to thrive and prosper in an increasingly digital world as the world is fast getting into knowledge economy.

Digital literacy on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises

The use of digital technology for businesses needs to be accompanied by good digital literacy to encourage SMEs' performance to be more optimal (Trinugroho, Pamungkas, Wiwoho, Damayanti & Pramono 2021). Multiple studies have shown that digital transformation in SMEs improves strategic outcomes (Jia et al., 2024). Selwyn (2020) points out that digital literacy is not a singular skill but a complex and dynamic process that unfolds across a continuum of engagement with digital technologies. Livingstone and Helsper (2019) state that it is important to recognize the different levels of digital literacy and to provide appropriate support for individuals at each stage of their development. It is not a static endpoint but an ongoing process of learning, adaptation, and evolution (Mousa, 2021). Digital literacy refers to the adoption of modern digital technologies like mobile devices, artificial intelligence, cloud computing, block chain, and the Internet of Things to enhance business operations (Gill et al., 2019). It involves a strategic approach to integrating these technologies throughout a company to bring about significant improvements in SME's businesses. This shift not only changes how businesses operate but also impacts how individuals and groups interact and create value using technology (Luftman et al., 1993). Using digital technology for SMEs is a new opportunity and challenge for business people (Ilyas, Munir, Tamsah, Mustafa & Yusriadi, 2021). Successfully embracing digital literacy requires SMEs to invest in specific technological and organizational capabilities, including knowledge management, information processing, and digital networking (Sabri, 2022). It involves using digital technology to improve an enterprises ability to use and integrate new tech into its operations. Digital literacy is crucial for all SME's who want their businesses to grow. The challenge of making organisation's employees digitally savvy can seem enormous, but it is also necessary for productivity, creativity, and growth . Heitin, (2016) established that the extant literature on digital literacy, skills and competencies is rich in definitions and classifications, but there is still no consensus on the larger themes and subsumed themes categories. . It is relevant for almost every job role, whether it is a sales professional using customer relationship management (CRM) software to nurture an important client relationship, or a product manager using a unified communications and collaboration solution to direct an important call to an executive. Digital literacy in education, students must develop specific digital literacy skills when reading and interacting with online content that may contain embedded resources such as hyper links, audio clips, graphs, or charts that require students to make choices, (Twinkl,2022). Digital literacy refers to

someone's ability to use IT and digital technology to find, evaluate, create and communicate information," says Matt Dunne. SMEs face several challenges and lapses due to low levels of digital literacy, hindering their ability to fully leverage digital technologies and compete in the digital age (Hargittai, 2019). The owners of SMEs and employees may not fully understand the benefits and potential of digital technologies for their businesses, this lack of awareness can lead to reluctance to invest in digital tools and training.

Database management on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises

Database Management Systems (DMS) emerged in the 1960s to address the problem of storing and retrieving large amounts of data accurately and quickly. An early of such system was IBM's Information Management System (IMS), which was widely deployed for more than 50 years later (Olofson, 2009). IMS stores data hierarchically, but in the 1970s Ted Codd proposed an alternative relational storage model based on set theory and predicate logic and the familiar concepts of tables, rows, and columns. In 1981, the first commercially available relational database management system (RDBMS) was released by Oracle. Enterprises are adopting emerging digital technologies to create efficiencies in their business processes, reduce costs, retain customers, and maintain a competitive advantage over competitor. For small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which constitute a significant portion of the global economy, developing a data management solutions is paramount in fostering innovation, enhancing competitiveness, and driving sustainable growth (Oyewole et al., 2024; Ediae et al., 2024). It provides SMEs with the tools to analyze market trends, customer behavior, and operational performance in real-time, leading to more accurate and timely decisions (Gupta et al., 2021). Secondly, it also enhances operational efficiency. The increasing reliance on data-driven decision-making across various sectors has accentuated the importance of data management, particularly for small and medium enterprises SMEs (Jejenywa et al., 2024) (Roux et al., 2023). As SMEs grow, the volume of data they generate and collect increases exponentially, as data volumes grow, so do the risks associated with data breaches and cyber attacks occurs. Data management is defined as "a group of activities relating to the planning, development, implementation, and administration of systems for the acquisition, storage, security, retrieval, dissemination, archiving and disposal of data. Data management is an important asset to any enterprise because it supports effective business management (Olajide, 2019). Data storage is the foundation of any data solution, and its scalability is critical for managing growing datasets. That is why data security and compliance are top priorities for small businesses, particularly in industries with strict regulatory requirements or sensitive customer data. Traditional data management technologies and methods are inefficient, expensive, and not equipped to handle, store and process large growing volumes of heterogeneous data (Adam, 2015). Off-the-shelf software solutions may not always provide adequate security measures or compliance features tailored to the business's specific needs. Software development enables small businesses to implement robust security protocols,

encryption standards, and access controls to protect sensitive data and ensure compliance with industry regulations. Microsoft Azure, and Google Cloud Platform, offer scalable storage options that allow businesses to pay for only the storage they use (Kaushik et al., 2021). These platforms provide virtually unlimited storage capacity, enabling SMEs to scale their storage needs up or down based on demand. Cloud storage also offers redundancy and data replication across multiple geographic locations, ensuring high availability and disaster recovery

Coleman, 2016 argues that knowledge, resources, and data management are three components that create resistance towards big data adoption in SMEs. The landscape of data management for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) is continuously evolving, driven by technological advancements and changing business needs. As SMEs seek to harness the power of data for competitive advantage, several key trends are shaping the future of scalable data solutions. Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) technologies are poised to data management for SMEs, enabling intelligent data processing, predictive analytics, and automation (Awan et al., 2021; Oyeniyi et al., 2024).

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology model by Venkatesh in 2003. The study was anchored on unified theory of acceptance and use of technology because it explains the many reasons why organizations use digital literacy to enhance their service delivery, as well as the possible factors that influence it. To provide a holistic understanding of technology acceptance, (Venkatesh et al., 2003) set the objective for developing a unified theory of technology acceptance by integrating key constructs predicting behavioural intention and use. Given the consequences of technology adoption on organizations' performance and a cost-revenue structure, the technology utilization-acceptance gap remains one of the major areas of research in the IS literature. Numerous models/theories had been introduced to understand the acceptance of the technology, which cumulatively explained 40% of the variance in technology use intention (Davis, 1989; Davis, Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1989; Taylor & Todd, 1995; Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). The models had roots in different disciplines, which limited the applications of these theories to certain contexts. To provide a holistic understanding of technology acceptance, (Venkatesh et al., 2003) set the objective for developing a unified theory of technology acceptance by integrating key constructs predicting behavioural intention and use. To fulfill this objective, the seminal acceptance literature was reviewed to draw up theoretical and contextual similarities and differences among technology acceptance theories originating from three research streams – i.e. social psychology, IS management and behavioural psychology (see (Venkatesh et al., 2003)).

Empirical Review

Abouelmayd (2017) asserted IT plays a crucial role in oil and gas business for the improvement of business process. The study concluded on the significant impact of IT infrastructure

nonperformance of oil and gas firms in Egypt. The duo examined the role of IT on organizational performance of banking and manufacturing companies in Pakistan and concluded the banking sector performed better on IT usage as against the manufacturing sector. The financial sector keep splaying a dominant role on the usage of investment on IT as against the manufacturing sector (Shaukatand Zafarullah 2019).

Kariuki (2015) in his findings disclosed a positive relationship of IT and organizational performance at Kenya Population Services. The study recommended corporate organizations are toembrace use of IT for efficient service delivery and further study should be executed on the challenges-confronting organizations using IT in Kenya.

Alam, Mulyadi, and Setyarko (2023) investigated the impact of digital technology, digital literacy, and digital marketing on the performance of SMEs in Bekasi, West Java. The research employed a quantitative methodology via a survey approach. Data for the study were gathered via a questionnaire method, utilizing a sample of 338 respondents through convenience and snowball sampling techniques. The research data was analyzed using SPSS software version 25.0. Multiple regression analysis was employed to determine the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable. This study's findings indicate that digital technology, digital literacy, and digital marketing significantly and positively influence SME performance.

Methodology

The study used descriptive survey as its research design. This is because according to Nworgu (2015), descriptive survey research design involves the collection of opinions, attitudes or feelings of a population orbits representative sample using questionnaire or interview to explain existing phenomenon. The study was carried out in South East, Nigeria. South East is one of the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria representing both a geographic and political region of the country's inland southeast. It comprises five States Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo State. Three hundred and sixty six (366) SMEs were considered from major urban cities of each state and this made up the population of the study. Complete enumeration was adopted and as all the selected SMEs were used. A five-point Likert structured questionnaire was used in collecting data from respondents. The arrangement of the codes are as follows: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1). Face and content validity were used to validate the research instrument. Reliability analysis run with Cronbach Alpha indicates high internal consistency (see table 1 below). The alpha coefficients showed that software development, digital literacy and database management scored; 0.984, 0.983, 0.973, respectively

Table I: Reliability Analysis

Variable	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha
Software development	5	0.984
Digital literacy	4	0.983
Data management	5	0.973

The alpha coefficients showed that Software development, Digital literacy, Data management scored 0.984, 0.983, 0.973, respectively.

Socio-Economic Profile of SME's in South East

152 (41.5%) of the SMEs engage in selling of finished products, 87 (21.8%) are involved in manufacturing whereas 127 (34.7) of them provide various degrees of services. The result of the demographic analysis showed that the targeted SMEs had the capacity to participate in the survey.

The research also showed that 28 (7.7%) of the SMEs had existed in less than one years, 11 5 (31.4%) for 1-3 years, 74 (20.2%) for 4-6 years, 80 (21.9%), 7-10 years for, 69 (18.9%) for 10 years and above, respectively and these SMEs had been in different lines of business. In addition, SMEs who render services outnumbered the SME's engaged in manufacturing and selling of finished products followed by the later.

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Software development does not have any significant influence on the performance of small and medium enterprises

Table Ii: The extent to which software development influence the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises

Variable	Beta	t value	R Square	F value	Sig.
(Constant)		-5.906			.000
Software Development	.984	104.346	.968	10888.019	.000

Author's computation, 2025

The result determined a positive, statistical relationship between software development and performance of small and medium enterprises in South East, Nigeria where (Beta = 0.98, t = 104.35, r² = .968, F = 10888.019, p < .01). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. The result showed that 97% change in the performance of SMEs was associated with change in the software development of the SME in question. This shows that software development of the SME exerts high level of influence on performance of SMEs in Southeast, Nigeria. The result implies that software development was an important predictor for performance of SMEs in Southeast, Nigeria. Changes in software

development tendencies of SMEs tend to influence changes in performance of SME. This implies that the software development in is, the higher its sales grows and vice versa.

Hypothesis Two:

Ho₂: Digital Literacy does not significantly influence performance of SMEs in Southeast.

Table Iii: The extent to which digital literacy influence performance of Smes

Variable	Beta	t value	R Square	F value	Sig
(Constant)		8.979			.000
Digital Literacy	.532	11.998	.283	143.954	.000

Author's computation, 2025

The research ascertained that digital literacy has a significant relationship with performance of SMEs in Southeast, Nigeria where (Beta = 0.53, t = 11.998, r² = .283, F = 143.954, p < .01). Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. The result also showed that 28% change in a firm's performance was associated with change in the SMEs digital literacy. It shows that digital literacy of a SME exerts low level of influence on the performance of SMEs. The research indicated that digital literacy of an SMEs slightly predicts the performance of the firm. In other word, changes in a firm's digital literacy had a little influence on the SMEs performance. Nevertheless, digital literacy in SME tend to experience greater performance in SMEs.

Hypothesis Three:

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between database management and performance of SMEs in Southeast Nigeria.

TABLE 4: The Extent To Which Database Management influence performance Of SMEs

Variable	Beta	t value	R Square	F value	Sig.
(Constant)	1.207				.228
Database Management	.980	94.388	.961	8909.048	.000

Author's computation, 2025

The result showed database management has a significant influence performance of SMEs in Southeast, Nigeria where (Beta = 0.98, t = 94.388, r² = .961, F = 8909.048, p < .01). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. It was also established that 96% database management of SMEs in Southeast, Nigeria was related to change in the SMEs performance. Thus, database management exerts high degree of influence on performance of SMEs. The research has established that database management was a key predictor performance of SMEs. SMEs which secures their data through data management tend to improve performance of SMEs.

Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

The result showed a positive, statistical relationship between software development and performance of SMEs in Southeast, Nigeria.

The digital literacy has significant relationship with performance of SMEs in Southeast, Nigeria

The result showed a significant, statistical relationship between database management in performance of SMEs in Southeast, Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study findings showed that for SMEs in Nigeria, especially the Southeast to realize their full potential and play their role accordingly, they cannot afford to ignore the application of information technology. However, from the survey results, the disadvantages of using information technology surpass the disadvantages. Finally, it is safe to draw conclusion from the results of this research that the use of information technology is relevant in the effective management of SMEs in Nigeria. These findings validate the theories utilized in this study which is the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology model by Venkatesh in 2003

Recommendations

- i. SMEs owners and managers should be committed in getting used to information technology through digital literacy, that will help develop a business software and also secure their data through database management for an improved performance of SMEs
- ii. Government should improve on the electricity supply in the country in every region so that the technology can be put to maximum use to achieve a better performance of SMEs
- iii. Governments of South-East States should create conducive environment and provide constant and low-cost electricity tariff so that SMEs operators will be able to compete favourably with their foreign counter-parts, thereby making South-East the economic hub of Nigeria.
- iv. Governments of South-East States should ensure that support services such as proper financing of SMEs, provision of adequate infrastructure like ICT facilities, and access to modern technologies are provided for SMEs operators.

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